

Determinants of Work-Life Balance among Elderly Caregivers: Mixed Method Approach

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Abstract: Work-Life Balance is one of the main challenges for modern societies. This is because it affects the well-being and productivity of workers, as well as their ability to enjoy their personal life. One in five Malaysians felt stressed and faced difficulty ensuring they could manage their work and family simultaneously. Therefore, this study intends to investigate the relationship between family, individual, job, and work-life balance of elderly caregivers. A mixed method is applied to conduct this study. Quantitative data were randomly obtained from 90 elderly caregivers from Malaysia, and qualitative data were collected through interviews and observation to verify the quantitative findings. The empirical analysis data suggest that job, family and individual significantly impact the work-life balance of elderly caregivers. Qualitative results support job, family and individual instruments in both strongest and lowest influence on the work-life balance among caregivers. This study makes two important contributions in light of the growing interest in the work-life balance of elderly caregivers. The outcomes of the study are likely to aid the development of literature on professionals that take care of older people. This study also sheds light on understanding the important determinants of work-life balance and helps policymakers to support the well-being of these caregivers.

Keywords: Malaysia, elderly, work-life balance, work-family, caregivers.

Determinantes do Equilíbrio entre Vida Pessoal e Profissional em Cuidadores de Idosos: Abordagem de Método Misto

Resumo: Work-Life Balance é um dos principais desafios para as sociedades modernas. Isso ocorre porque afeta o bem-estar e a produtividade dos trabalhadores, bem como sua capacidade de aproveitar sua vida pessoal. Um em cada cinco malaios sentiu-se stressado e enfrentou dificuldades para garantir que pudesse administrar seu trabalho e sua família simultaneamente. Portanto, este estudo pretende investigar a relação entre família, indivíduo, trabalho e equilíbrio entre a vida profissional e profissional de cuidadores de idosos. Um método misto é aplicado para conduzir este estudo. Os dados quantitativos foram obtidos aleatoriamente de 90 cuidadores de idosos da Malásia, e os dados qualitativos foram coletados por meio de entrevistas e observação para verificar os achados quantitativos. Os dados da análise empírica sugerem que o trabalho, a família e o indivíduo impactam significativamente o equilíbrio entre vida pessoal e profissional dos cuidadores de idosos. Os resultados qualitativos apoiam os instrumentos de trabalho, família e individuais na influência mais forte e mais baixa no equilíbrio entre vida pessoal e profissional entre os cuidadores. Este estudo traz duas contribuições importantes à luz do crescente interesse no equilíbrio trabalho-vida dos cuidadores de idosos. Os resultados do estudo provavelmente auxiliarão no desenvolvimento de literatura sobre profissionais que cuidam de idosos. Este estudo também lança luz sobre a compreensão dos importantes determinantes do equilíbrio entre vida profissional e pessoal e ajuda os formuladores de políticas a apoiar o bem-estar desses cuidadores.

Palavras-chave: Malásia, idosos, conciliação trabalho-família, trabalho-família, cuidadores.

1. Introduction

Work-Life Balance (WLB) is one of the main challenges for modern societies. This is because it affects the well-being and productivity of workers, as well as their ability to enjoy their personal life. Zulfiqar et al., (2020) stated that there are many factors and perceptions about the selection of organizations between men and women. Gender-focused have different preferences in selecting a work, especially women responsible for housekeeping, child, and family care. It is very good if the caregiver can have a WLB culture between work and family. However, the balance concerns also may be appealing to men. The failure to do so might bring a negative impact, whether to work or family matters.

A study by Heger and Korfhage (2020), entitled 'Short-and Medium-Term Effects of Informal Eldercare on Labour Market Outcomes' explained that children often with a hard decision whether they want to assist their parents with personal care or household chores or maybe being in the industry. Caregiving can show a feeling of purpose or strengthen family bonds; however, it is emotionally and physically demanding and needs much time. Thus, serving as an informal caregiver often competes with workforce involvement. As a result, caregivers may be required to pay certain costs of decreasing regular working hours or dropping out of the workforce. This can result in a loss of income, a reduction in pension benefits and a lower chance of future employment or promotion. Such caregiving opportunity costs may be much higher if the negative relationship continues over time, whether if the caregiver lasts for an extended period or if the negative effects continue long aftercare has ended. For example, if the caregivers are unable to get any job again after the caregiving for parents has ended due to market frictions or economic problems, the caregiver has not only insufficient labour income but also expected future income (Coe et al., 2018). From this aspect, there are a lot of studies that show a negative relationship between care activities and employment participation (Bauer & Sousa-Poza, 2015).

That seems to be a common problem in an employee's life. Nowadays, finding a job is difficult since many candidates want to be recruited into an organization. The Department of Statistics Malaysia also reported that the unemployment rate increased from 3.3 % in 2019 to 5.3% in May 2020. Khairunneezam (2011) stated that employees intend to leave the organization because of several factors, such as the level of satisfaction with the work and non-work domains, for example, family, friends, and others. It can be a big problem once the employee decides to leave the industry or quit. However, the best way for the employee to do this is to be recruited and retained in the organization. The organization must also do its best to ensure its retention program is successful for the precious employees.

Furthermore, this problem has attracted more attention in the field of research studies. Rozanti and Salmiah (2014) found that one in five Malaysians felt stressed and faced difficulty ensuring they could manage their work and family simultaneously. The same survey also explained that about two-thirds of the respondents placed their family before work, while the others were trying to balance work and family life. Haslinda and Ying (2016) also discovered that job satisfaction among married professional women in Malaysia will be affected due to conflicts between work and family. Another study on Malaysian academics stated that the perceived work-life balance correlates negatively with the intention to leave the organization (Khairunneezam, 2011). Therefore, this research intends to investigate the determinants of the WLB of caregivers.

2. Literature review

WLB refers to the capacity to reconcile a successful career with personal or family obligations. In other words, it is the capacity to meet the demands of one's professional and personal life and to experience fulfilment in all aspects of life (Reverberi et al., 2021). However, doing so can be very challenging and impact an individual's satisfaction in their roles as an employee or as a family member (Khairunneezam, 2011). The balance between work and life is very important since it will bring negative effects if it is not appropriately managed by the individual. Khairunneezam (2011) also mentioned that work-life balance has crucial consequences on the employees' life and organization; however, it is given less attention because not all people feel that work-life balance is an important aspect of life. Many studies have shown that work-life conflict leads to work, personal/family, and health effects. For example, research by Gautam and Jain (2018) showed that employees experience significant stress while balancing their job and personal lives, affecting their performance at work and home. Another study by Ross and Vasantha (2014) found a significant impact on people's lifestyles due to increased working hours, which will harm their mental well-being. Inadequate work-life balance also impacts a working individual's performance at work and in their personal life (AlHazemi & Ali, 2016).

However, in order to know the concept, we need to understand the definition of the principles of WLB (Khairunneezam, 2011). From the WLB concept, we can divide it into three words: 'work', 'life' and 'balance' which shows the argument of balancing between two important things in the individual world: work and life. In order to get the WLB, individuals need to manage their life properly and not all people can balance them well. Based on a study by Rozanti and Salmiah (2014), the researchers shared a research result done in Selangor among 120 married female secretaries who experienced lower work satisfaction and family dissatisfaction due to work-family conflict. Meanwhile, Siti Aisyah et al., (2012) found that work-family conflict is strongly associated with stress and psychological pressure, while Kim and Windsor (2015) mentioned that WLB can also affect employee turnover intention.

WLB is where the individual needs to balance the time for work and other aspects of life. Personal interests, social and recreational activities, and, most importantly, family are all significant components of other aspects of life. Having a work-life balance also contributes to positive effects on the caregiver itself and the organization. Low turnover, work engagement, organizational citizenship behaviour, in-role performance, increased firm productivity, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment are some of the positive effects of WLB in the workplace (Konrad & Mangel, 2000). It is supported by research from Denson, Szelenyi and Bresonis (2018) that achieving a better WLB can benefit employers in terms of having a more productive and less stressful workforce. It is because they feel valued by the company, attracting more candidates, improving productivity, decreasing employee turnover, gaining a reputation as an employer of choice, and retaining employees who are important to the organization. WLB is an important aspect of an employee's life; however, it is not emphasized in all organizations because most organizations value their profits more than the employee's well-being. Most bosses and companies fail to recognize that work and life are inextricably linked, necessitating a work-life balance in order to improve employee well-being. Most bosses regard WLB as a fad and opt to ignore it (Jayasingam et al., 2021). Employees not only want development in their careers but are in need of well-being in their personal life. Day by day, employees are beginning to realize the importance of WLB which tends to affect the employees' decision

to stay in an organization. This is because employees desire a flexible work schedule that allows them to take care of their personal and professional lives without neglecting them (Kossivi et al., 2016).

Malaysia will be also an aged society by 2044, with 14% of its population aged 65 and over, the number of Malaysians over 65 years old is expected to quadruple from two million now to over six million by 2040 (The World Bank, 2020). In line with the rapid growth of the elderly, it gives pros and cons to the society and economy where the demographic trend nowadays of the busyness of children to balance their career and family has become more challenging. The situation became a challenge not only to the children but also to the government and community in settling the problem of older people. However, due to the current situation, today's young generation has to leave their parents due to migration and some have family conflicts (Yusoff et al., 2018). Consequently, many older people have no choice but to be sent to old folks or nursing homes and in the worst case, they have been abandoned there for years or maybe forever.

2.1 Job

Job or known as work, is any action that involves either physical or mental effort to produce something or achieve a goal. An individual performs duty as an obligation to his employers for consideration or as an obligation to other people, such as family, friends, or even self. Job-related factors play an important role in work-life balance. It can impact work-life balance in a variety of ways. Employers can take steps to promote WLB, such as offering flexible work arrangements, providing resources for stress management, and fostering a supportive work environment (Mintzberg, 2021). According to Armstrong and Taylor (2014), performance is a behaviour of how goals are met. Aside from Human Resource Management (HRM), how to manage people is to get the best out of them and 'the best' is very subjective to each individual. The best can mean high performance, or it could be shown by the individual behaviour where the employees practice extra effort, care, innovation, and productivity in their job.

However, there are several factors that influence employees' behaviour and performance which are motivation, commitment, and engagement (Wilkinson et al., 2010). Due to the work-oriented factors, employees often choose to change because of career advancement and better training programs, however, the organization cannot depend on those factors to make the employees stay longer. Lindfelt et al. (2018) were having a similar thought where they highlighted that the decreasing turnover rate could be achieved if the organization delivered proper training and standard performance appraisal to the employees. Hence, the demand for an individual to handle work and also family will lead to a conflict where the employee does not know which one to prioritize. Previous studies on the consequences of work-life conflict have found that most employees faced more time and strain-based conflict compared to behaviour-based conflict. Based on Isa et al. (2018), the situation arises because there is often interference of roles between work and family which occurs due to time-based (i.e.: working hours, work and family involvement), and strain-based (role ambiguity, work and family tension, role conflict and caretaker demand). Haslinda and Ying (2016) have discussed work-related factors in all types of professions due to the concept's universality, and the factors that have been identified are; role autonomy, role ambiguity, role conflict, work overload, long hours working and perceived job threat. On the positive side, a balance of work-life can improve overall psychological well-being and increase satisfaction in the work and family domains.

Therefore, a hypothesis has been developed as follows:

H1: There is a significant relationship between a job and the caregiver's work-life balance.

2.2 Family

According to established definitions, a family is a group of two or more individuals, with one designated as the householder, who share a common living space and are connected by either biological, marital, or adoptive ties (Steel et al., 2012). A family might be made up of a single person or several unrelated individuals or families living together. A literature review has established that a family can be categorized into two which are main family structure and spousal support. Family is very important to an individual that can give good support in an employee's career. Kwok et al. (2015) discovered that family emotional support influenced one's levels of optimism and self-efficacy, leading to higher job satisfaction. However, some may have a conflict in order to balance both work and family. Soomro et al. (2018) found that work-life balance, work-family conflict and family-work conflict all have moderating effects on perceived employee performance. A study by Stone et al. (1987) showed that the caregivers who quit their job are only 8.9%, in terms of the effect of long-term care, the caregivers tend to be the ones who work for reduced hours which is at 21%, the caregivers who changed their schedule (29.4%) or the ones who take unpaid leave is 18.6%. However, Ikeda (2017) found out that 80% of the research respondents feel that working caregivers do not need a long-term leave or only need a short-term leave for only one week or less via the long-term care insurance system. By having the system, the employees can have a long-term care service due to the availability of the caregiving service. Therefore, the hypothesis has been developed as follows:

H2: There is a significant relationship between family and the work-life balance of the caregiver.

2.3 Individual

Individuals contribute to numerous facets of WLB, including gender, marital status, life and career stages, and which personality is most frequently mentioned (Haslinda & Ying, 2016). The gender dimension, however, perpetuates the traditional notion of women as mothers and wives. Most people believe that women, not males, should be the primary caregivers for their families, both in terms of raising children and taking care of elderly or ill members. Yet, as a result of their caregiving responsibilities, many women see a decline in their paid job hours, reducing their chances of re-entering the workforce (Ehrlich et al., 2020). In contemporary western societies, women's employment is affected by a prolonged withdrawal from the workforce or reduction in working hours due to their role as a caregiver to their family members such as partners, parents, parents-in-law, or others who need care due to poor health, disability, or age-related problem (Ehrlich et al., 2020). In addition, an individual's personality also affects how she or he views the aspect of work-life balance. According to Noraini (2003), there are two major elements of personality which are neuroticism and extraversion. An individual with a high tendency to overemphasize the negative sides of their experience is called neuroticism and tends to show greater stress. On the other hand, individuals who have a positive attitude and feel good about themselves and their surroundings tend to have good mental health. Haslinda and Ying (2016) discovered that 39.5% of the respondents disagreed with a statement that works rather than family was their major source of satisfaction in life. It shows that most of

the respondents look at the family aspects as more important than their work. This is because family is one of the individual's support systems to have good mental health. Therefore, a hypothesis has been developed as follows:

H3: There is a significant relationship between individuals and the work-life balance of the caregiver.

3. Methodology

This study derives the framework from the past literature review and Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1991). This theory explains attitudes, subjective norms and perceived behavioural towards the intention of performing the behaviour. Figure 1 shows a model of the hypothesized relationships investigated in this study.

Figure 1- Research framework

The following hypotheses have been developed as follows:

H1: There is a significant relationship between a job and the caregiver's work-life balance.

H2: There is a significant relationship between family and the work-life balance of the caregiver.

H3: There is a significant relationship between individuals and the work-life balance of the caregiver.

This study employed a mixed-method approach to enrich the findings. Explanatory sequential designs are applied, beginning with the quantitative analysis. According to Creswell and Clark (2018), quantitative data is collected and followed up with interviews to help explain the reasons behind and meaning of the quantitative survey results. First, quantitative is applied to analyse the relationship of the instruments through descriptive analysis, reliability analysis and regression analysis.

This study used purposive sampling due to the involvement of specific target groups and participant characteristics. Purposive sampling is employed when the researcher wants to target a specific population with certain features or experiences, or when the study needs a specific type of participant (Palinkas et al., 2015). In this context of the study, the respondents are the caregiver of the elderly in Malaysia. The data of this study are derived from responses provided during the actual survey. Surveys have been identified as valuable methods for investigating patterns in obtained data and are commonly utilised successfully in consumer research (Easterby-Smith et al., 1993). According to Zikmund (2003), the sample size can be 30 or more units, although Sekaran (2003) stated between 30 and 500 units, hence 90 respondents were chosen for this

study. Surveys have been identified as valuable methods for investigating patterns in obtained data and are commonly utilised successfully in consumer research (Easterby-Smith et al., 1993).

Hayman's (2005) version of the Work/Life Balance Self-Assessment scale was adapted to examine factors affecting scholarly productivity and work/life balance. As explained in more detail, the survey for this research consists of five (5) sections namely "demographics profile", "work-life balance", "job", "family", and "individual". An online survey was adopted and distributed using Google Forms. Those items of the questions are adapted from previous studies and are measured using a 5 Likert scale ranging from (1) = strongly disagree, (2) = disagree, (3) = neutral, (4) = agree and (5) = strongly agree.

The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 26, was used to do frequency analysis, descriptive analysis, reliability analysis, and multiple regression analysis. Frequency analysis is used to calculate the percentile of respondents' profiles in terms of gender, ethics, age, religion, marital status, and monthly income. For descriptive analysis, mean and standard deviation are computed.

The internal consistency of the items in their respective factors is examined using the reliability test. Internal consistency reliability measures how well items on a scale or instrument measure the same concept over time (Maulana, Widodo, & Hidayatullah, 2021). Instrument dependability relates to the instrument's applicability and consistency in evaluating concepts that are devoid of bias and error (Sekaran & Bougie, 2010). It also ensures that the method's many components are measured consistently throughout time. Cronbach's Alpha is a common reliability coefficient used to show how strongly the items in the instrument are positively linked with one another. It computes the mean intercorrelations between the concept's measurement pieces. While there are some broad rules for interpreting alpha values in reliability analysis, there is no absolute agreement on what level of internal consistency dependability is acceptable or desirable (Streiner, 2003). According to Sekaran and Bougie (2010), if Cronbach's Alpha is closer to 1, the measures of reliability will be better. Cronbach's Alpha of 0.5 or 0.6 is considered poor, but valid, 0.7 is acceptable, and 0.8 or 0.9 is considered good or very good. The cut-off value for assessing reliability in this study will be 0.5.

Furthermore, multiple regression analysis is frequently used to test the hypotheses proposed earlier. It is a statistical approach used to investigate the relationship between two or more independent variables and a dependent variable. Multiple regression analysis seeks to determine which independent factors have a significant effect on the dependent variable and to estimate the size and direction of these effects (Chen et al., 2021).

While qualitative is needed in this study to support the quantitative analysis (in descriptive and regression analysis) through the semi-structured interview results. The explanatory sequential design is applied by first, getting quantitative data and analysing, getting the result, and determining the quantitative results to explain. Second, gather the qualitative data and analysis, get the results and finally, interpret how qualitative data explain the quantitative results.

The steps to gather qualitative data are by interviewing the respondents following purposive sampling. Respondents must be working adults who provide care for senior citizens in order to meet the criteria for this survey. According to Patton (2002), the use of purposeful sampling was chosen for the purpose of this study in order to acquire information that is comprehensive and insightful. There are five respondents participated in this study and they were interviewed through phone calls. The number of respondents is

sufficient for this study to verify the data as mentioned by Creswell and Clark (2018) as the final sample size is not determined until reaching saturation. The questions cover four categories: Job, Family, Individual, and WLB. Once the data has been collected and transcribed, then the data are analysed based on quantitative data findings (descriptive analysis and regression analysis) through the content analysis process.

4. Findings and Results

4.1 Quantitative Method

4.1.1 Frequency Analysis

As presented in Table 1, 62.2% of the respondents are female, while only 37.8% of the respondents are male. Out of 90 respondents, 12 respondents were aged between 18 and 29; 50 respondents were aged between 30 and 39; 16 respondents were aged between 40 and 49 and 12 respondents are at aged 50 years and above. Moreover, 66.7% of the respondents are married, while respondents who are single and others comprise 31.1% and 2.2%, respectively.

Table 1- Respondents' Profiles

Classification	Description	Frequency	Per cent
Gender	Male	34	37.8
	Female	56	62.2
Age	18-29	12	13.3
	30-39	50	55.6
	40-49	16	17.6
	50 and above	12	13.3
Marital Status	Single	28	31.1
	Married	60	66.7
	Others	2	2.2
Race	Malay	74	82.2
	Chinese	4	4.4
	Indian	2	2.2
	Others: Khmer	10	11.1
Monthly Gross Income	RM2500 and below	28	31.1
	RM2501 to RM5000	18	20.0
	RM5001 to RM7000	12	13.3
	RM7001 and above	32	35.6
Number of Care Recipients	One	60	66.7
	Two	28	31.1
	More than two	2	2.2
Duration of Care Provided	Less than 1 year	22	24.4
	1-2 years	18	20.0
	3-4 years	20	22.2
	5-9 years	16	17.8
	More than 10 years	14	15.6

Most of the respondents are Malay (82.2%), followed by Others (11.1%), Chinese (4.4%) and Indian (2.2%). Furthermore, most of the respondents have monthly scale salary ranges of about RM7,001 and above (35.6%), while the lowest number of

respondents who have monthly salaries is between RM5,001 to RM7,000 (13.30%). Out of 90 respondents, 60 respondents have one care recipient and 28 respondents have two care recipients; while 2 respondents have more than two care recipients. Most of the respondents have less than a 1-year duration of care provided (24.4%), while the lowest number of respondents have more than 10 years of care provided (15.6%).

4.1.2 Descriptive Analysis

The descriptive analysis shown in Table 2 illustrates the results. First of all, in relation to "Family", the item "My family matters come first, then work" has the highest mean of 4.089 and "My family members help me with the household responsibilities" obtains the lowest mean of 3.867. This indicates that "My family matters come first, then work" has an influential factor in ensuring the caregivers have a better WLB. Based on a 5-point scale for family elements with regard to caregivers' WLB, the mean of 4.089 shows that the majority of respondents agree or strongly agree.

Table 2 - Descriptive Analysis

Variables	Items	Mean	Standard Deviation
Family	My family understand the nature of my job demands.	3.889	0.529
	My family members help me with household responsibilities.	3.867	0.584
	My family members help me with the caregiving duties.	3.933	0.614
	I worry about my care recipient when I am at work.	3.978	0.779
	I think about my family matters when I am at work.	3.956	0.820
	My family matters come first, then work.	4.089	0.788
Individual	I am happy with my current personal achievement at work.	3.600	0.614
	I do not have any health conditions diagnosed (by Health Practitioners) suffer due to work obligations.	3.844	0.559
	I wish I had more time to do things for myself.	3.379	0.773
	I prefer focusing on my self-development to working long hours in the office.	3.333	0.764
	My family understand my goals in life.	3.800	0.545
	My employer provides room for my personal development	3.600	0.684
Job	I am happy with the current position that I am in.	3.556	0.620
	My family understands my career goal.	3.756	0.526
	I feel that I am rewarded accordingly by the organisation.	3.489	0.623
	Despite my commitment as a caregiver, my employer provides room for career growth.	3.578	0.580
	I am not actively looking for another employment.	3.622	0.680
	I feel that it is important to be successful in my career.	3.978	0.497
Work-Life Balance	The organization provides support in ensuring a positive work-life balance.	3.511	0.585
	I have difficulty balancing the demands of my family with my work.	2.800	0.753
	I have difficulty balancing my personal matters with my work.	2.867	0.753
	I have difficulty balancing my work obligations with my personal matters.	2.667	0.793
	I have difficulty pursuing my career growth due to family matters	4.067	0.445

Moreover, regarding “Individual”, “*I do not have any health conditions diagnosed (by Health Practitioners) suffer due to work obligations*” has the highest mean of 3.844 while “*I prefer focusing on my self-development to working long hours in the office*” has the lowest mean of 3.333. This informs that “*I do not have any health conditions diagnosed (by Health Practitioners) suffer due to work obligations.*” has the strongest influence on individual towards caregivers’ perception of WLB. On a 5-point scale, many of the respondents are lenient toward agreeing about having “Individual” towards caregivers’ WLB, as indicated by mean of 3.844 on the scale.

Furthermore, when looking at the variable of “Job” reveals that “*I feel that it is important to be successful in my career*” has the greatest mean of 3.978, whilst “*I feel that I am rewarded accordingly by the organisation*” has the lowest mean of 3.489. As a result, the finding shows that “*I feel that it is important to be successful in my career*” has the greatest effect on caregivers’ WLB. The mean of 3.978 on a five-point scale for “Job” suggests that the majority of the respondents feel that this aspect is important in attaining the WLB of caregivers. Finally, the variable “Work life balance” demonstrates that “*I have difficulty pursuing my career growth due to family matters*” has the highest mean of 4.067 and “*I have difficulty balancing my work obligations with my personal matters*” has the lowest mean of 2.667. With that being said, the analysis found that “*I have difficulty pursuing my career growth due to family matters*” has the greatest influence on work-life balance towards caregivers. The mean of 4.067 on a 5-point scale for “Work-Life Balance” believes that most of the respondents are lenient to agree on the relevance of this factor in gaining work-life balance among the caregivers.

4.1.3 Reliability Analysis

Table 3 shows the results of reliability testing. The alpha coefficient for Family Elements is 0.827, which is considered good. The result for measuring Self Elements is 0.546, which is considered poor. The outcome of the Career Elements test of caregivers’ work-life balance is 0.808, which is categorized as good. Finally, the result for the measurement of Work-Life Balance is 0.553, which is considered poor. Generally, all of the coefficients obtained for the Likert Scale questions are valid, in spite the poor consistency of two of them. The main characteristics are maintained.

Table 3 - Reliability Analysis

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of items
Family Elements	0.827	6
Self-Elements	0.546	6
Career Elements	0.808	6
Work-Life Balance	0.553	5

4.1.4 Regression Analysis

R Square indicates the percentage variance in the dependent variable that is explained by the variation in the independent variables (Taylor, 2023). The R Square of 0.165 implies that all the independent variables explain 16.5 per cent of the variance in the dependent variable. 83.5 per cent of the variance in the dependent variable is not explained by the independent variables in this study. This indicates there are other

independent variables that are not included in this study and could further strengthen the regression equation. As in Table 4, the analysis shows that the variable for Family Elements is not significant. It is because the p-value for the Family Elements variable is 0.823 (82.3%), which is above the 5% significant level. Hence, Family Elements are not related to the dependent variable (WLB). Furthermore, Self Elements has a p-value of 0.292 (29.2%), which is above the 5% significant level. Therefore, the Self Elements variable is not significant. Therefore, Self Elements are also not related to the dependent variable (Work-Life Balance). However, only Career Elements has a p-value that is less than 5% significant level, a p-value of 0.41 (4.1%). Therefore, the Career Elements variable is significant. Thus, the Career Elements are positively related to the dependent variable (WLB).

Table 4- Regression analysis

	Hypotheses	Beta	t-test	p-value	supported
H1	Family Elements positively influence work-life balance among caregivers.	-0.024	-0.224	0.823	No
H2	Individual Elements positively influence work-life balance among caregivers.	0.151	1.061	0.292	No
H3	Job Elements positively influence work-life balance among caregivers.	-0.265	2.080	0.041	Yes

4.2 Qualitative Data

The purpose of qualitative data analysis is to produce rich and detailed descriptions of the phenomena being studied, and to generate insights that are grounded in the experiences and perspectives of the participants. Table 5 summarizes the respondent's profile including the elderly background.

The descriptive analysis in the quantitative method shows the strongest and lowest findings of the instruments on a work-life balance among the caregivers. To strengthen the findings, qualitative results explain the quantitative analysis.

In Family elements, for the strongest influence "*My family matters come first, then work*", the result shows that R1 to R5 stated if their parents are sick and need aid, they will come first, whether applying for emergency leave or contact their siblings to ask who can reach first to their elderly. Or else they will take turns among siblings to take care of their elderly. The respondents mention that:

– *"I have a husband and my sister to reach our parents if anything happens. So far, my working hours are OK" (interview 1)*

Table 5 - Respondent's (R) profile and elderly background

R	Gender	Age	Employment	Income	Marital status	Relationship with elderly	Stage of health (mild/chronic)	Duration of caring for the elderly	Elderly working experienced
1	F	Above 40	Full-time	Above RM5k	Married	Parent	Chronic.	More than 5 years	Own business
2	F	Below 40	Full-time	Below RM5k	Single	Father	Chronic	More than 5 years	Govt sectors
3	F	Above 40	Part-time	Below RM5k	Married	Mother	Chronic	Less than 5 years	Not mention
4	F	Above 40	Full-time	Above RM5k	Divorce	Mother	Mild	Less than 5 years	Govt sectors
5	F	Below 40	Full-time	Below RM5k	Married	Mother	Chronic	Less than 5 years	Govt sectors

However, for the lowest influence in “*My family members help me with the household responsibilities*”, the R1 to R5 agree that there are no difficulties as their parents still can walk (but slowly), chores work is not a big issue because their parents stay with them or with their siblings. Additionally, the respondents also mention that:

- _ “*I have siblings to take care of. Normally, we take turns caring for her. For this month, my mother stays at my house*” (interview 3)
- _ “*My mother can manage herself. She is OK because her friends (neighbours) are around her*” (interview 4)

For Individual analysis, “*I do not have any health conditions diagnosed (by health Practitioners) suffer due to work obligations*” is the strongest influence on a work-life balance among the caregivers. The age of the respondents (R1 to R5) is between 32 to 50, and they agree that they are in good shape (good health). For “*I prefer focusing on my self-development to working long hours in the office*”, respondents R1-R5 agree that working long hours in the office is the lowest influence on the balance between work and family.

The result for the Job in qualitative shows the respondents R1 to R5 agree that “*I feel that it is important to be successful in my career*” is the strongest influence on a work-life balance among the caregivers. As they are at the age of 32 to 50, their marital status contributes to the success in their career as they look for a brighter future.

Respondent mentions that:

- _ “*I need to further my study to develop my own career advancement*” (interview 2).

Whilst, “*I feel that I am rewarded accordingly by the organisation*” is the lowest influence towards the job on a work-life balance among caregivers. For work-life balance, the strongest influence is “*I have difficulty pursuing my job (career) growth due to family matters*” as stated by the respondents:

- _ “*Even I have a husband and my sister to reach our parents if anything happens. But sometimes, yes I am tired*” (interview 1).
- _ “*Yeah...can be said so. But I am OK*” (interview 2).
- _ “*I have siblings to take care of. So, I am also old but this is my responsibility as a daughter*” (interview 3).
- _ “*I have to be strong for my mother*” (interview 4).
- _ “*Sometimes...but, still I am her children*” (interview 5).

This analysis suggested that most of the respondents are lenient to agree on the relevance of this factor in gaining work-life balance among the caregivers. However, for the lowest influence, “*I have difficulty balancing my work obligations with my personal matters*”, the qualitative result shows that R1-R5 said that the major satisfaction is a balance between work and family.

In Job, table 6 shows the summary of the data interpretation which qualitative analysis supports the quantitative analysis.

Table 6-Summary of the data interpretation in which qualitative analysis supports the quantitative analysis in descriptive analysis

	Quantitative	Qualitative
Family	Strongest influence: "My family matters come first, then work"	R1-R5 – Respondents stated that if their parents are sick and need aid, they will come first, whether applying for emergency leave or contacting their siblings to ask who can reach first to their elderly. Or else they will take turns among siblings to care for their elderly.
	Lowest influence: "My family members help me with the household responsibilities"	R1-R5 – Respondents do not have difficulties as their parents still can walk (but slowly), and chores work is not a big issue because their parents stay with them or with their siblings.
Individual	Strongest influence: "I do not have any health conditions diagnosed (by health Practitioners) suffer due to work obligations"	R1-R5 – Respondents agree that they are in good health.
	Lowest influence: "I prefer focusing on my self-development to working long hours in the office"	R1-R5 – Respondents agree.
Job	Strongest influence: "I feel that it is important to be successful in my career"	R1-R5 – Respondents agree. However, they mentioned that they sometimes have problems balancing their job and personal well-being.
	Lowest influence: "I feel that I am rewarded accordingly by the organization"	R1-R4 – Respondents agree.
WLB	Strongest influence: "I have difficulty pursuing my career growth due to family matters"	R1-R5 – Respondents agree.
	Lowest influence: "I have difficulty balancing my work obligations with my personal matters"	R1-R5 said that the major satisfaction is a balance between work and family

Based on Table 6, the qualitative results support the quantitative data which shows that family, job and individual are significant as shown in Table 7.

Table 7- Significant and insignificant results based on qualitative data

	Significant relationship with the work-life balance of the caregiver	Insignificant relationship with the work-life balance of the caregiver
Job	Yes	Yes
Family	Yes	No
Individual	Yes	No

The result shows that the quantitative findings are supported by the qualitative results through two analyses: descriptive analysis and regression analysis. These were

explained in descriptive and regression analysis, where both quantitative and qualitative show similar results. Qualitative results support job, family and individual instruments in both strongest and lowest influence on a work-life balance among caregivers.

5. Discussion of results and conclusion

This study seeks to examine the correlation among job, family, and individual factors in relation to the work-life balance of elderly caregivers. The study revealed a statistically significant correlation between the caregiver's work-life balance and the variables of job, family, and individual factors. The findings support the notion that achieving a balance between one's professional and personal life is essential for fostering long-term social and economic development. Achieving sustainable social and economic growth requires a well-balanced and productive workforce. This is where job and individual work-life balance come into play. A healthy work-life balance is essential in ensuring that individuals are productive and motivated at work, leading to increased job satisfaction and reduced turnover rates. This, in turn, benefits organizations by improving their reputation, productivity, and profitability (Naudé, Rothmann & Du Plessis, 2022). Moreover, a balanced work-life helps individuals maintain good mental and physical health. When employees have time to relax and recharge outside of work, they are more productive and focused when they return to work. This can help to reduce stress and burnout, leading to a more engaged and committed workforce. A healthy workforce, in turn, contributes to the sustainability of social and economic growth (Baeriswyl et al., 2022).

Balanced work-life also leads to increased creativity and innovation. When individuals have time to pursue their passions and interests outside of work, they bring a fresh perspective and new ideas to the workplace. This can lead to increased efficiency, better problem-solving, and improved decision-making, all of which contribute to the sustainable growth of organizations and the economy as a whole (Cho & Kim, 2021). Finally, WLB is essential in promoting equality and social inclusion. A balanced work-life allows individuals to participate in social activities, community engagement, and family life. This, in turn, helps to build a more inclusive society where everyone has equal opportunities to participate and contribute to social and economic growth (Ruokolainen et al., 2021).

Employees are the most important resource in an organization. Their value for the organization is not only to recruit the best talent, but they also need to be retained in that organization for the long term (Bauer and Sousa-Poza, 2015). The Department of Statistics Malaysia has reported that the labour force participation rate in the country is increasing from time to time. In 2019, it was 68.6% and rose to 68.9% in January 2020 which is higher than the previous year. In Malaysia, more than half of the nation's population is actively working, and managing work commitments along with life commitments requires appropriate balance on the individual's part (Haslinda and Ying, 2016). Employees should not focus only on their work commitments but need to divide their time for life commitments such as self-time (Rozanti and Salmiah, 2014). As an individual, having a work-life balance is very crucial. Research done by Rozanti and Salmiah (2014) showed that one in five Malaysians feel much stressed and face work-life conflict where they have difficulties in managing work and family at the same time. The problem became more serious when the turnover rate increased. However, many people are not able to focus on several things in their life at once and it may have negative effects. For example, employees who work as full-timers, have the possibility of not being able to

take care of their parents well, especially during the parents' older age and need assistance in their daily life (Bauer and Sousa-Poza, 2015).

This study makes two important contributions in light of the growing interest in the work-life balance of elderly caregivers. The outcomes of the study are likely to aid the development of literature on the elderly. Finally, this study sheds light on understanding the important determinants of the caregiver's work-life balance.

There are a few limitations that may offer directions for future researchers in this area. To begin, this research examines the job, family, and individual of work-life balance of the caregiver. As a result, future research may wish to look at additional factors that influence the work-life balance of the caregiver, such as the location of the workplace and the salary of the caregiver. Next, the sample of this study is relatively small. The future researcher could increase the number of samples from various states in Malaysia. Although this sample size meets the minimum requirement for multivariate analysis (Hair et al., 2019), larger samples are able to inflate the statistical power. In addition, this research is confined to a quantitative method. As a result, a mixed-method approach with an in-depth interview might be used to better understand the participant's responses.

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7. References

- AlHazemi, A. A., & Ali, W. (2016). The Notion of Work-Life Balance, Determining Factors, Antecedents and Consequences: A Comprehensive Literature Survey. *International Journal of Academic Research and Reflection*, 4(8), 74-85.
- Armstrong, M., & Taylor, S. (2014). *Armstrong's Handbook of Human Resource Management Practice*. Kogan Page Limited.
- Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behaviour. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, Volume 50, Issue 2, 179-211.
- Baeriswyl, S., Krause, A., Schwaninger, A., & Udrisard, D. (2022). Work-Life Balance During the COVID-19 Pandemic: The Role of Job Insecurity and Psychological Detachment. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(3), 1258. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19031258>
- Bauer, J. M., & Sousa-Poza, A. (2015). Impacts of informal caregiving on caregiver employment, health, and family. *Journal of Population Ageing*, 8(3), 113–145. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12062-015-9116-0>
- Chen, Y. Y., Chen, M. C., Lee, J. S., & Lin, C. H. (2021). The Impact of Age, Physical Activity, and Perceived Barriers on Subjective Health Status among Community-Dwelling Older Adults in Taiwan: A Multiple Regression Analysis. *Journal of Aging and Health*, 33(3-4), 291-303. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0898264320981841>

- Cho, Y. J., & Kim, M. (2021). The Relationship Between Work-Life Balance and Employee Engagement: The Moderating Role of Job Autonomy. *Journal of Business Research*, 130, 650-660. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.03.008>
- Coe, N. B., Skira, M. M., & Larson, E. B. (2018). A Comprehensive Measure of the Costs of Caring for a Parent: Differences According to Functional Status. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*, 66(10), 2003–2008. Doi: <http://10.0.4.87/jgs.15552>
- Creswell & Clark (2018). *Designing and Conducting Mixed-Method Research (3rd Edition)*. SAGE Publication
- Denson, N., Szelenyi, K., & Bresonis, K. (2018). Correlates of Work-Life Balance for Faculty Across Racial/Ethnic Groups. *Research in Higher Education*, 59. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11162-017-9464-0>
- Easterby-Smith, M., Thorpe, R., & Lowe, A. (1993). *Management Research: An Introduction*. Sage Publications
- Ehrlich, U., Möhring, K., & Drobníč, S. (2020). What Comes after Caring? The Impact of Family Care on Women's Employment. *Journal of Family Issues*, 41(9), 1387–1419. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0192513X19880934>
- Gautam, I., & Jain, S. (2018). A Study of Work-Life Balance: Challenges and Solutions. *International Journal of Research in Engineering, IT and Social Sciences*, 198-217.
- Hair, J. F., Risher, J. J., Sarstedt, M., & Ringle, C. M. (2019). When to Use and How to Report the Results of PLS-SEM. *European Business Review*, 31(1), 2–24. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1108/EBR-11-2018-0203>
- Haslinda, A., & Ying, C. K. (2016). Work-Life Conflict among University Employees in a Private Higher Education Institution in Malaysia. *International Journal of Advances in Social Science and Humanities, Volume 04, Issue 04*.
- Hayman, J. 2005. Psychometric Assessment of an Instrument Designed to Measure Work Life Balance. *Research and Practice in Human Resource Management* 13 (1): 85-91.
- Heger, D., & Korfhage, T. (2020). Short- and Medium-Term Effects of Informal Eldercare on Labor Market Outcomes. *Feminist Economics*, 0(0), 1–23. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13545701.2020.1786594>
- Ikeda, S. (2017). Family Care Leave and Job Quitting Due to Caregiving: Focus on the Need for Long-Term Leave. *Japan Labor Review*, 14(1), 25–44.
- Isa, N. M., Kaur, H., Singh, A. P. L., & Hashim, R. (2018). Job Stress, Work-to-Family Conflict and Social Support in the Education Industry. *Journal of Administrative Science*, 15(3), 1–17.
- Jayasingam, S., Lee, S. T., & Mohd Zain, K. N. (2021). Demystifying the life Domain in Work-Life Balance: A Malaysian Perspective. *Current Psychology*, 1-12.
- Khairunneezam, M. N. (2011). Work-Life Balance and Intention to Leave among Academics in Malaysian Public Higher Education Institutions. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2(11), 240–248.
- Kim, M., & Windsor, C. (2015). Resilience and Work-Life Balance in First-Line Nurse Manager. *Asian Nursing Research*, 9(1), 21–27. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anr.2014.09.003>
- Konrad, A. M., & Mangel, R. (2000). The Impact of Work-Life Programs on Firm Productivity. *Strategic Management Journal*, 21(12), 1225–1237. Doi: [https://doi.org/10.1002/1097-0266\(200012\)21:12](https://doi.org/10.1002/1097-0266(200012)21:12)
- Kossivi, B., Xu, M., & Kalgora, B. (2016). Study on Determining Factors of Employee Retention.

- Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 04(05), 261–268. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.4236/jss.2016.45029>
- Kwok, S.Y.C.L., Cheng, L., & Wong, D.F.K. (2015). Family Emotional Support, Positive Psychological Capital and Job Satisfaction among Chinese White-Collar Workers. *J Happiness Stud* 16, 561–582. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10902-014-9522-7>
- Lindfelt, T., Ip, E. J., Gomez, A., & Barnett, M. J. (2018). The Impact of Work-Life Balance on Intention to Stay in Academia: Results From a National Survey of Pharmacy Faculty. *Research in Social and Administrative Pharmacy*, 14(4), 387–390.
- Maulana, R., Widodo, A., & Hidayatullah, M. A. (2021). Validity and Reliability of a Career Decision-Making Self-Efficacy Scale for Indonesian High School Students. *Journal of Career Development*, 48(2), 214-228. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0894845320954621>
- Mintzberg, H. (2021). The Nature of Work-Life Balance. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 35(2), 147-163. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5465/amp.2019.0192>
- Naudé, L., Rothmann, S., & Du Plessis, M. (2022). The Relationship between Work-Life Balance and Employee Engagement: The Role of Proactive Personality. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 27(1), 75-86. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1037/ocp0000323>
- Noraini, M. N. (2003). Work- and Family-Related Variables, Work-Family Conflict and Women's Well-Being: Some Observations. *Community, Work & Family*, 6(3), 297–319. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/1366880032000143474>
- Palinkas, L. A., Horwitz, S. M., Green, C. A., Wisdom, J. P., Duan, N., & Hoagwood, K. (2015). Purposeful Sampling for Qualitative Data Collection and Analysis in Mixed Method Implementation Research. *Administration and Policy in Mental Health and Mental Health Services Research*, 42(5), 533-544. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10488-013-0528-y>
- Patton, M. Q. (2002). *Qualitative Research and Evaluation Methods (3rd Edition)*. SAGE Publication
- Reverberi, E., Manzi, C., Van Laar, C., & Meeussen, L. (2021). The Impact of Poor Work-Life Balance and Unshared Home Responsibilities on Work-Gender Identity Integration. *Self and Identity*, 1-20.
- Ross, D. S., & Vasantha, S. (2014). A Conceptual Study on Impact of Stress on Work-Life Balance. *Sai Om Journal of Commerce & Management*, 1(2), 61-65.
- Rozanti, A. H., & Salmiah, M. A. (2014). Work-Family Conflict and Work-Family Enrichment and Their Consequences in Malaysia. *Middle-East Journal Of Scientific Research*, 19(5), 729–733. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5829/idosi.mejsr.2014.19.5.21020>
- Ruokolainen, M., Pahkin, K., Mauno, S., Mäkikangas, A., & Kinnunen, U. (2021). Work-life Balance and Health among Healthcare Professionals: The Role of Job Demands and Resources. *Work & Stress*, 35(3), 288-307. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02678373.2021.1926652>
- Sekaran, U. (2003). *Research Methods for Business (4th ed.)*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2010). *Research Methods for Business: A Skill-Building Approach (5th ed.)*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Siti Aisyah, P., Siti Khadijah, Z. B., & Azizah, R. (2012). Work-Family Conflict and Work Related Attitude: The Mediating Effects of Stress Reactions. *International Journal of Social Science and Humanity Studies*, 4, 377–387.
- Soomro, A.A., Breitenecker, R.J. & Shah, S.A.M. (2018). Relation of Work-Life Balance, Work-Family Conflict, and Family-Work Conflict with the Employee Performance-Moderating Role of Job Satisfaction. *South Asian Journal of Business Studies*, Vol. 7 No. 1, pp. 129-146. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1108/SAJBS-02-2017-0018>

- Steel, L., Kidd, W., & Brown, A. (2012). *The Family (2nd ed.)*. Palgrave MacMillan.
- Stone, R., Cafferata, G. L., & Sangl, J. (1987). Caregivers of the Frail Elderly: A National Profile. *The Gerontologist*, 27(5), 616–626. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1093/geront/27.5.616>
- Streiner, D. L. (2003). Starting at the Beginning: An Introduction to Coefficient Alpha and Internal Consistency. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 80(1), 99-103. Doi: https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327752JPA8001_18
- Taylor, S. (2023). What is R-Squared? Retrieved January 2023, from <https://corporatefinanceinstitute.com/resources/data-science/r-squared/>
- The World Bank. (2020). A Silver Lining: Productive and Inclusive Aging for Malaysia. Retrieved January, 2023, from <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/malaysia/publication/a-silver-lining-productive-and-inclusive-aging-for-malaysia>
- Wilkinson, A., Bacon, N., Redman, T., & Snell, S. (2010). *The SAGE Handbook of Human Resource Management*. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.4135/9780857021496>
- Yusoff, N. M., Sumarjan, N., Zamri, M. T., Jamal, S. A., & Chik, C. T. (2018). Conceptualization of Senior Living Community in Malaysia. *Advanced Science Letters*, 24(1), 375–377. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1166/asl.2018.12013>
- Zikmund, W. G. (2003). *Business Research Methods (7th edition ed.)*. Ohio: Thomson.
- Zulfiqar, A. I., Qandeel, H., Rabbia, Z., & Tayyaba, R. (2020). Problems in Recruitment. *International Journal of Management Excellence*, 14(2), 2091–2094. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.17722/ijme.v14i2.1134>